

RESEARCH ARTICLE

EVALUATING *E-PEMANTAUAN KLINIKAL*: A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON SUSTAINABLE CLINICAL SUPERVISION AT TRAINING INSTITUTE, MINISTRY OF HEALTH, MALAYSIA, KOTA KINABALU**Bondi, M.E.* , Osman, M., Erek, A.L., Jatin, M.M., Lijawa, F., Anuar, A., Justin @ Mohd Aman, S.I.S., Hamdan, N., Siaulin, J., Made, I.N., Smile, I., Abd Razi, R., Awang, M.S.**

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Abstract

Background: Efficient and accurate clinical supervision reporting is critical for ensuring quality assurance and accountability in healthcare training institutions. However, traditional paper-based documentation methods are often inefficient, costly, and unsustainable. This study aimed to evaluate the implementation of *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* at the Training Institute, Ministry of Health Malaysia (ILKKM), Kota Kinabalu, by examining its impact on clinical supervision efficiency, operational cost savings, and user satisfaction.

Methodology: This quasi-experimental pre-post study assessed the impact of the system on documentation time, cost savings, paper usage, and user satisfaction. Data on user satisfaction were collected using a self-administered Likert-scale questionnaire distributed to clinical instructors and academic staff (n = 90) using a convenience sampling method. Documentation time was estimated through structured staff feedback, while cost and paper usage data were retrieved from institutional procurement records. The platform was developed using Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) and Cross-Platform, Apache, MariaDB, PHP, and Perl (XAMPP), accessible via computers and mobile devices, and included encrypted login and real-time reporting functions. The intervention was implemented over 21 months, supported by echo-based training sessions. Data was analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27.

Results: Results revealed a significant reduction in report processing time (from 30 -80 minutes to 10 – 20 minutes) and cost savings of MYR47,206 (USD11,119) annually. User satisfaction scores significantly increased from M = 3.2 (SD = 0.7) to M = 4.8 (SD = 0.3), $t(89) = 10.45$, $p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = 1.10$. The system also eliminated the use of 468 reams (234,000 sheets) of paper annually.

Conclusion: These findings highlight the effectiveness of *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* in improving efficiency, reducing environmental impact, and supporting digital healthcare transformation. The system presents a scalable model for enhancing clinical supervision across healthcare training institutions, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

Keywords: digital supervision, clinical education, SDGs, healthcare digitalisation, user satisfaction, digital dream

Introduction

Accurate and timely clinical supervision reporting is a critical component of healthcare education, enabling institutions to monitor learner progress, ensure compliance with training standards, and support data-informed decision-making. Clinical supervision not only ensures the competency of trainees but also plays a critical role in upholding institutional standards and patient safety (Grealish et al., 2018). Effective supervision documentation serves as an evidence base for curriculum evaluation, regulatory audits, and the professional development of both trainees and supervisors.

At ILKMM Kota Kinabalu, clinical supervision was traditionally documented using paper-based forms. Internal reporting audits conducted in 2021 and 2022 revealed persistent inefficiencies in this system, including inconsistent data capture, illegible handwriting, misplaced documents, and excessive consumption of printing resources such as paper and toner. These limitations were shown to hinder institutional oversight and compromise the sustainability and scalability of supervision documentation practices (ILKMM Kota Kinabalu, Internal Supervision Report, 2022).

Challenges associated with paper-based supervision are not unique to Malaysia. Several low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) have reported similar barriers, including limited audit trails, data fragmentation, and lack of timeliness in evaluations (Woodward et al., 2022). In response, many institutions have begun shifting towards digital documentation systems to improve efficiency, reduce waste, and ensure the availability of structured, retrievable data for decision-making. These changes align with broader trends in digital governance and implementation science, which emphasise the importance of user-centred, scalable systems to support organisational transformation (Greenhalgh et al., 2017).

In response to these challenges, Digital Dream team in ILKMM Kota Kinabalu developed and implemented *e-Pemantauan Klinikal*, a secure, web-based platform for real-time clinical supervision documentation. The system was designed to enhance reporting efficiency, improve user experience, and promote institutional sustainability. This study evaluated the extent to which these objectives were achieved by examining changes in documentation time, user satisfaction levels, and reductions in resource consumption and operational costs following implementation. This initiative is aligned with the Health Digital Transformation 2021 – 2025 Blueprint issued by the Ministry of Health Malaysia (2021), and support Malaysia's national commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 3 (Good Health and Well-being), Goal 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), and Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) (Economic Planning Unit, 2021; United Nations, 2015).

Globally, similar efforts have been undertaken in Saudi Arabia, Brazil, and other LMICs, where digital supervision tools have been adopted to improve data accuracy, reduce operational waste, and enhance accessibility of documentation (Alasmari et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2022). These trends are consistent with the Global Strategy on Digital Health by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), which promotes the use of digital platforms to strengthen health systems through innovation and accountability. This study aimed to evaluate the implementation of *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* at ILKMM Kota Kinabalu by examining its impact on clinical supervision efficiency, operational cost-savings, and user satisfaction.

Methods

This quasi-experimental pre-post study was conducted at the ILKKM Kota Kinabalu as part of a digital innovation initiative aimed at improving clinical supervision documentation through technological transformation. The *e-Pematauan Klinikal* platform was developed using PHP and deployed via XAMPP. It was designed for accessibility across both desktop and mobile devices and included key features such as secure login, encrypted data storage, real-time reporting dashboards, and user-friendly interfaces to support seamless clinical documentations.

The implementation process followed five structured phases: 1) development and testing, 2) prototype validation, 3) echo training sessions with users, 4) full deployment across departments, and 5) post-implementation evaluation, as outlined in **Table 1**. In the final phase, the system was evaluated based on user feedback and measurable outcomes. Data collection involved a self-administered structured questionnaire distributed to clinical instructors, educators, and academic leaders (n = 90) who had used the platform for at least one complete posting cycle. The questionnaire assessed user satisfaction, system usability, and perceived impact on supervision documentation processes using a 5-point Likert scale. In addition, operational data on documentation time were estimated through staff feedback and verified against standard operating procedures, while procurement records were reviewed to calculate cost and paper savings related to printing, toner, and photocopying.

Quantitative data were collected from 90 users, comprising clinical instructors, educators, heads of programmes, the Deputy Director (Academic), and the Director of ILKKM Kota Kinabalu. A convenience sampling method was used to target those directly involved in clinical supervision, with the aim of evaluating satisfaction with the new system.

Table 1: Implementation phases of the project

Phases	Activities
Phase 1: Development and Testing	System architecture was designed; functionalities were developed using PHP and XAMPP; internal testing was conducted by the Digital Dream Team to ensure stability and security
Phase 2: Prototype Validation	A working prototype was piloted selected users (instructors and administrators); feedback on usability and layout was collected and applied for system refinement
Phase 3: Echo Training	Comprehensive hands-on training sessions (echo model) were held for all clinical instructors and educators to ensure familiarity with the system and to troubleshoot usage issues
Phase 4: Full Deployment	The finalised system was launched across all departments at ILKKM Kota Kinabalu; ongoing technical support was provided for real-time usage and documentation
Phase 5: Post-Implementation Evaluation	User satisfaction surveys were conducted three months after full development, allowing users to complete at least one cycle using the platform. Data on cost savings, time efficiency, and environmental impact were collected and analysed using SPSS version 27 to evaluate the outcomes of the system implementation

A self-administered survey was used to assess user satisfaction, incorporating a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Moderately Agree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree). The survey measured perceived usability, accessibility, and documentation experience. Additional data was collected to evaluate operational impact. Cost data specifically related to the clinical supervision documentation process, including expenditures on paper, toner, and photocopying, were extracted from the institute’s annual procurement records. Report documentation time was self-reported by users based on their actual experience before and after implementation of the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system. These responses were further cross-checked against estimates found in the institute’s standard operating procedures to ensure consistency and contextual accuracy.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS Version 27. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise baseline characteristics, cost, and time metrics. Paired-sample t-test was employed to assess pre- and post-implementation differences in satisfaction scores. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to verify assumptions of normality, and Cohen’s d was calculated to determine the magnitude of effect.

Results

The implementation of the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system resulted in measurable improvements in the documentation efficiency, operational cost savings, resource consumption, and perceived sustainability. Documentation efficiency was assessed based on self-reported estimates by users regarding the time required to complete supervision reports before and after system implementation. On average, reporting time decreased from 30 – 80 minutes to 10 – 20 minutes per report, indicating a reduction of 50% to 80% in time burden. Institutional sustainability was inferred from the elimination of paper-based documentation, which translated to significant savings on printing consumables and a reduction in paper waste. The total annual reduction in operational expenditures was calculated at MYR47,206 (USD11,119), comprising MYR5,616 in paper, MYR37,260 in toner, and MYR4,330 in photocopying expenses, as illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Annual cost savings by category. Breakdown of MYR47,206 saved annually, with toner and photocopying contributing to over 90% of total savings

It is important to note that the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system was developed in-house by the Digital Dream Team at ILKKM Kota Kinabalu using open-source tools (PHP and XAMPP), and incurred minimal financial cost for development and deployment. Because no external vendor or licensing fees were required, and implementation relied on existing institutional infrastructure and staff, the calculated cost savings are considered to outweigh the negligible development costs. Nevertheless, the absence of formal accounting records for development costs is acknowledged as a limitation in establishing net return on investment.

A significant improvement was also observed in documentation processing time. Prior to the implementation of the system, the average duration for completing clinical supervision reports ranged from 30 to 80 minutes. Following the adoption of the digital system, this was reduced to 10 to 20 minutes per report, resulting in an estimated improvement in efficiency of 50% to 80% (Figure 2). This reduction substantially eased the documentation burden on clinical instructors and administrative staff, contributing to more timely and streamlined report submissions.

Figure 2: Average report processing time. Average report time was reduced from 55 to 15 minutes, representing a 73% improvement

From an environmental sustainability perspective, the transition to a digital platform eliminated the use of approximately 468 reams of paper annually, which equates to 234,000 individual sheets (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Paper usage comparison. The system eliminated the use of 234,000 sheets of paper per year

This outcome directly aligns with the institutional sustainability goals of ILKMM Kota Kinabalu, which include reducing paper dependency, minimising operational waste, and improving cost-effectively in administrative processes. These goals are part of the broader MOH’s commitment to promoting sustainable healthcare education practices through the digitisation of routine operations. Furthermore, the project contributes to Malaysia’s national priorities under SDG 12, which emphasises responsible consumption and production, including efforts to reduce material waste and increase resource efficiency in government services. User satisfaction significantly increased following system implementation. The mean satisfaction score improved from 3.2 (SD = 0.7) prior to the digital transition to 4.8 (SD = 0.3) post-implementation. A paired-sample t-test confirmed the statistical significance of this increase, $t(89) = 10.45$, $p < 0.01$, with a large effect size (Cohen’s $d = 1.10$), indicating a strong positive impact of the system on user experience. Respondents consistently reported improvements in system usability, data accessibility, documentation clarity, and overall efficiency of the supervision process. A comprehensive summary of pre- and post-implementation performance across key indicators, documentation time, paper usage, cost, and satisfaction score is presented in **Table 2**, which supports the system’s measurable contributions to institutional efficiency, environmental sustainability, and user experience. A summary of key indicators tabulated in a comparison of outcomes before and after digital system implementation is presented in **Table 3**.

Table 2: User satisfaction (Mean ± SD)

Phase (n = 90)	Mean score	SD	p-value
Pre-implementation	3.2	0.7	< 0.001
Post-implementation	4.8	0.3	

Note: Satisfaction increased significantly from 3.2 ± 0.7 to 4.8 ± 0.3 ; $p < 0.01$, Cohen’s $d = 1.10$

Table 3: Summary of key indicators. Tabulated comparison of outcomes before and after digital system implementation

Indicator	Pre-implementation	Post-implementation	% change or gained
Time per report (min)	30 – 80	10 – 20	50 – 80% improvement
Paper usage (sheets/year)	234,000	0	100% reduction
Cost (MYR/year)	MYR47,206	0	Full elimination
Satisfaction score (mean ± SD)	3.2 ± 0.7	4.8 ± 0.3	Significant (p < 0.01)

Discussion

The findings from this study underscore the transformative potential of digital technologies in optimising clinical supervision practices within healthcare training institutions. The implementation of the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system at ILKMM Kota Kinabalu significantly reduced documentation time, operational costs, and paper usage, while markedly improving user satisfaction. These outcomes align with global trends in digital health transformation and echo the growing recognition that integrating technology into health education and service delivery is crucial to improving efficiency, transparency, and sustainability (WHO, 2021).

Digital health interventions are increasingly seen as catalysts for reform in healthcare systems, particularly in LMICs, where resource constraints often limit service delivery (Adane et al., 2020). According to Aung et al. (2022), digital platforms in healthcare education and monitoring significantly enhance task efficiency, data accuracy, and compliance with training standards, especially in settings where traditional documentation methods prevail. The present study affirms these conclusions, with users reporting substantial reductions in time spent on clinical supervision reports from an average of 30 - 80 minutes to just 10 – 20 minutes, demonstrating a 50 – 80% improvement in workflow efficiency.

The cost savings of MYR47,206 (USD11,119) annually underscore the economic benefit of implementing digital supervision systems. These savings stemmed from reductions in paper, toner, and photocopying expenses. Importantly, these savings were achieved without requiring external development expenditure, as the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system was designed and implemented internally using open-source platforms (PHP and XAMPP) by the ILKMM Digital Dream team. This in-house approach resulted in minimal financial outlay, thereby maximising the net operational return on investment. While formal cost-accounting for personnel time was not conducted, the absence of third-party development or licensing costs supports the sustainability and replicability of such digital solutions with government institutions.

This observation is consistent with the work of Serafini et al. (2020) and Hadi et al. (2023), who found that health facilities implementing electronic supervision tools experienced substantial reductions in consumable expenses, especially in document-heavy departments. Adane et al. (2020) further emphasised that digital health solutions in clinical settings not only improve documentation quality but also cut operational costs significantly, particularly in lower-resource environments.

User satisfaction is another key determinant of successful digital health adoption. In this study, the statistically significant increase in satisfaction scores from M = 3.2 (SD = 0.7) to M = 4.8 (SD = 0.3), with a large effect size (Cohen’s d = 1.10), signals strong user approval. Lee and Rho (2021)

similarly reported that perceived ease of use and system reliability are among the top predictors of digital system adoption among healthcare professionals, especially in nursing education. The acceptance of *e-Pemantauan Klinik* among ILKMM educators may be attributed to its intuitive interface, real-time access, and secure platform, all of which facilitated a smoother transition from manual reporting.

Moreover, the incorporation of structured echo-training sessions prior to and during system implementation likely contributed to high uptake. Carayon et al. (2018) highlighted, digital interventions in health institutions are most successful when paired with comprehensive, iterative training models. The echo model used at ILKMM Kota Kinabalu ensured continuous engagement, knowledge sharing, and digital literacy development among clinical instructors and administrative staff. The project addressed a major barrier often encountered in digital transformation initiatives through the development of institutional digital competency (Kellermann and Jones, 2013).

Another significant outcome of this project was its contribution to sustainability and environmental responsibility. The system effectively eliminated the use of 468 reams (approximately 234,000 sheets) of paper annually. This directly supports SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, which advocates for reduced material consumption and waste. Hadi et al (2023) demonstrated that sustainable operational practices in healthcare not only lower carbon footprints but also enhance institutional credibility and compliance with green health policies. The paperless transition at ILKMM exemplifies how digital innovation can support environmentally sound practices in public institutions (WHO, 2021).

The impact of the system also resonates with SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being, particularly in improving the quality and accountability of health workforce education. Digitising supervision documentation enabled ILKMM educators to record evaluations in real-time, minimise human error, and access trainee progress longitudinally. This ensures better feedback loops, standardised evaluations, and readiness for adults. Additionally, SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure is addressed by strengthening the digital backbone of the institution and reducing dependency on physical storage systems (Scott Kruse et al., 2016).

The findings of this study are consistent with global practices. For example, Alasmari et al. (2021) evaluated electronic clinical logbooks in Saudi Arabia and found improvements in supervision transparency, student accountability, and documentation integrity. Similarly, Santos et al. (2022) observed that the use of a mobile application for nursing supervision in Brazil led to enhanced communication between tutors and learners and reduced documentation errors. These studies suggest that digital supervision systems can be successfully adapted across different cultures and healthcare education systems.

Despite the positive outcomes, the implementation process was not without challenges. Initial resistance from some users was observed, particularly among staff less familiar with digital systems. This aligns with observations by Kellermann and Jones (2013), who noted that digital health adoption is frequently hindered by user apprehension, lack of digital literacy, and fear of workflow disruption. However, these concerns were largely mitigated through consistent technical support, targeted digital upskilling, and involvement of end users in feedback loops. Intermittent internet connectivity also posed challenges, but was addressed through infrastructure upgrades and offline data caching mechanisms.

Scalability is a key consideration for the future of *e-Pemantauan Klinikal*. Given its demonstrated efficiency and sustainability, the system is a strong candidate for implementation across other ILKKM branches nationwide. However, as noted by Hadi et al. (2023), scalability of digital health tools requires not just technical feasibility but also strong policy support, financing mechanisms, and stakeholder buy-in. The experience of ILKKM Kota Kinabalu could serve as a pilot for nationwide expansion, provided that the model is adapted to suit varied infrastructure capacities across different campuses.

Furthermore, this project complements national strategies, including Malaysia's Health Digital Transformation 2021 – 2025 blueprint, which emphasises the integration of digital platforms in public health and training institutions according to the National SDG Roadmap Phase II (Economic Planning Unit, 2021). Demonstrating local ownership, low development cost, and high impact, the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system serves as a model for other government institutions aiming the modernise workflows while promoting sustainability and quality assurance. The implementation of *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* has resulted in measurable gains across multiple domains: cost efficiency, workflow optimisation, user experience, and environmental sustainability. Alignment with SDGs 3, 9, and 12 reinforces Malaysia's commitment to building a digitally empowered and environmentally responsible health sector (Economic Planning Unit, 2021). As healthcare training continues to evolve into a more data-driven and competency-based model, innovations like this offer scalable and effective solutions for institutional reform and continuous reform and continuous quality enhancement.

Conclusion

The implementation of the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system has produced significant improvements in the efficiency of clinical supervision, achieved notable cost savings, and enhanced user satisfaction. The initiative reflects strong alignment with Malaysia's national digital health transformation priorities and supports broader global sustainability goals. This project demonstrates how locally developed digital solutions can modernise supervision practices, enhance institutional performance, and establish a scalable model for healthcare education reform across the country.

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Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of ILKMM Kota Kinabalu prior to data collection and approval from the Director General of Health, MOH [NIH.800-5/3/1 Jld 138 (16)]. This system has been registered under the Intellectual Property Corporation Act 1987 (CRLY2025S02140). This study also adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki, and all procedures were conducted in line with national and institutional research ethics guidelines.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to the conduct, analysis, or reporting of this study. The development and implementation of the *e-Pemantauan Klinikal* system were carried out as part of an institutional quality improvement initiative, without any commercial or financial incentives. No external funding bodies influenced the study design, data collection, interpretation, or decision to publish. All authors have independently contributed to the content and approved the final version of the manuscript for submission.

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